

Hyper-Kamiokande: Possible Contributions from Latin America

Thematic Areas: Neutrino Physics, Beyond Standard Model, Astroparticle Physics

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Abstract

Hyper-Kamiokande is a next generation large-scale water Cherenkov detector to be constructed in Japan based on the well established technology, a successor of the highly successful Super-Kamiokande detector, which discovered neutrino oscillations, leading to Nobel Prize in Physics in 2015. Its fiducial mass is 187 kton, about 8 times larger than that of Super-Kamiokande detector and 295 km away from the J-PARC neutrino beam line. Hyper-Kamiokande has a wide range of physics programs which include nucleon decay search, observation of CP violation in the neutrino sector, and observation of neutrinos from various astrophysical sources including Sun and supernovae with much better sensitivities than the previous experiments. This document was prepared mainly based on the Hyper-Kamiokande Design Report, arXiv:1805.04163 [physics.ins-det], written by the Hyper-Kamiokande Proto-Collaboration, by highlighting some of the main physics goals. While the Hyper-Kamiokande project has not yet been approved and funded by the Japanese government, its construction is expected to start soon in April 2020, and there is a good prospect to be approved soon. Currently, from Latin America, 2 faculty members from PUC-Rio/Brazil are participating in the Hyper-Kamiokande proto-collaboration. We describe briefly our possible contributions to the Hyper-Kamiokande project.

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I. SCIENTIFIC CONTEXT

Hyper-Kamiokande (Hyper-K or HK) [1] is a large-scale next generation underground water Cherenkov detector to be built in Japan, a successor of Super-Kamiokande detector which discovered neutrino oscillations by observing atmospheric neutrinos [2]. Hyper-K plans to adopt the staging approach which implies that the experiment will start taking data with a single tank which has a total (fiducial) mass of 258 (187) kton and located 295 km away from the J-PARC neutrino beam facility. The detector has a cylindrical form with the height of 78 m and the diameter of 74 m. In Fig. 1 we show the schematic view for the configuration of single cylindrical tank instrumented with high density (40% photocoverage) photomultipliers (PMTs) [1].

FIG. 1. Schematic view for the configuration of single cylindrical tank instrumented with high density (40% photocoverage) PMTs. Taken from [1].

After the first tank starts operating, there is a plan to build the second tank which is supposed to have the identical size and performance in some location which can be either inside or outside Japan. Indeed there is a possibility to have the second detector in Korea which is currently under discussion within the HK proto-collaboration [4]. The Hyper-K is expected to carry out a wide range of physics programs including the precise measurement of the CP phase which allow us to establish CP violation at high significance if the CP phase turns out to be very different from 0 or π [3], discovery or improvement of the current limits for nucleon decay search and observation

of neutrinos from astrophysical sources such as Sun and supernovae with unprecedented sensitivities or indirect search for dark matter. In Table I we show the summary of sensitivities for the main physics programs of Hyper-K described in details in [1]. In this document, we briefly highlight some of them.

TABLE I. Expected sensitivities of the Hyper-Kamiokande experiment assuming 1 tank for 10 years. Taken from [1].

Physics Target	Sensitivity	Conditions
Neutrino study w/ J-PARC ν		1.3 MW \times 10 ⁸ sec
– CP phase precision	$< 23^\circ$	@ $\sin^2 2\theta_{13} = 0.1$, mass hierarchy known
– CPV discovery coverage	76% (3σ), 57% (5σ)	@ $\sin^2 2\theta_{13} = 0.1$, mass hierarchy known
– $\sin^2 \theta_{23}$	± 0.017	1σ @ $\sin^2 \theta_{23} = 0.5$
Atmospheric neutrino study		10 years observation
– MH determination	$> 2.2\sigma$ CL	@ $\sin^2 \theta_{23} > 0.4$
– θ_{23} octant determination	$> 3\sigma$ CL	@ $ \theta_{23} - 45^\circ > 4^\circ$
Atmospheric and Beam Combination		10 years observation
– MH determination	$> 3.8\sigma$ CL	@ $\sin^2 \theta_{23} > 0.4$
– θ_{23} octant determination	$> 3\sigma$ CL	@ $ \theta_{23} - 45^\circ > 2.3^\circ$
Nucleon Decay Searches		1.9 Mton-year exposure
– $p \rightarrow e^+ + \pi^0$	7.8×10^{34} yrs (90% CL UL)	
	6.3×10^{34} yrs (3σ discovery)	
– $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu} + K^+$	3.2×10^{34} yrs (90% CL UL)	
	2.0×10^{34} yrs (3σ discovery)	
Astrophysical neutrino sources		
– ^8B ν from Sun	130 ν 's / day	4.5 MeV threshold (visible energy) w/ osc.
– Supernova burst ν	54,000–90,000 ν 's	@ Galactic center (10 kpc)
	~ 10 ν 's	@ M31 (Andromeda galaxy)
– Supernova relic ν	70 ν 's / 10 years	10–30 MeV, 4.2σ non-zero significance
– WIMP annihilation in the Earth		10 years observation
(σ_{SD} : WIMP-proton spin dependent cross section)	$\sigma_{SD} = 10^{-40}\text{cm}^2$	@ $M_{\text{WIMP}} = 10\text{GeV}$, $\chi\chi \rightarrow b\bar{b}$ dominant
	$\sigma_{SD} = 10^{-44}\text{cm}^2$	@ $M_{\text{WIMP}} = 50\text{GeV}$, $\chi\chi \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ dominant

II. OBJECTIVES

Main objectives of Hyper-K experiment are the high precision long-baseline neutrino oscillation studies, in particular, observation of CP violation (or conservation) in the lepton sector with high

significance, the observation of nucleon decay or significant improvement of the current limits of nucleon decay lifetime, and the study of various astrophysical neutrino sources, including Sun and supernovae as well as indirect search of dark matter, with significantly higher sensitivities than previous experiments.

III. METHODOLOGY

Below we describe the methodology for the main physics goals of HK.

A. Observation of CP violation in neutrino oscillations.

The flavor mixing of neutrinos is described as follows by using the 3×3 unitary matrix, U , often called PMNS (Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata) or MNS (Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata) matrix [5, 6],

$$\nu_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^3 U_{\alpha i} \nu_i \quad (\alpha = e, \mu, \tau), \quad (1)$$

where ν_α ($\alpha = e, \mu, \tau$) and ν_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) denote neutrino fields with definite flavor and mass, respectively. The standard parameterization of the mixing matrix, which can be found, e.g, in [7], is given as

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{CP}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta_{CP}} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\alpha_{21}}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\frac{\alpha_{31}}{2}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $c_{ij} \equiv \cos \theta_{ij}$, $s_{ij} \equiv \sin \theta_{ij}$, and δ_{CP} , often called the Dirac CP phase, is the Kobayashi-Maskawa type CP phase [8] in the lepton sector. The 2 additional phases, α_{21} and α_{31} , are Majorana CP phases which exist if and only if neutrinos are of Majorana type. We note that neutrino oscillations are not sensitive to these Majorana CP phases, therefore, they are not directly relevant for the HK experiment, though they can be studied by neutrinoless double beta decay experiments.

In vacuum, the oscillation probability of $\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta$ ($\alpha, \beta = e, \mu, \tau$) for ultrarelativistic neutrinos is given by,

$$P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = \left| \sum_{i=1}^3 U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\beta i} e^{-i\frac{m_i^2}{2E_\nu} L} \right|^2 \\ = \delta_{\alpha\beta} - 4 \sum_{i>j} \Re(U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta i} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta m_{ij}^2}{4E_\nu} L \right) + 2 \sum_{i>j} \Im(U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\alpha j} U_{\beta i} U_{\beta j}^*) \sin \left(\frac{\Delta m_{ij}^2}{2E_\nu} L \right), \quad (3)$$

where E_ν is the neutrino energy, L is the baseline, $\Delta m_{ij}^2 \equiv m_i^2 - m_j^2$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$) are the mass squared differences with m_i and m_j being the neutrino masses. For the CP conjugate channel, $\bar{\nu}_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\beta$, the same expression in Eq. (3) holds, but the matrix U is replaced by its complex conjugate (or equivalently $\delta_{CP} \rightarrow -\delta_{CP}$ in Eq. (2)), resulting in the third term in Eq. (3) switching its sign.

The magnitude of the CP violation in neutrino oscillation can be characterized by the difference of probabilities between neutrino and anti-neutrino channels, which, in vacuum, can be easily computed by using Eq. (3), and is given by

$$\Delta P_{\alpha\beta} \equiv P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) - P(\bar{\nu}_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\beta) = 16J_{\alpha\beta} \sin \Delta_{21} \sin \Delta_{32} \sin \Delta_{31}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$J_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \Im(U_{\alpha 1} U_{\alpha 2}^* U_{\beta 1}^* U_{\beta 2}) = \pm J_{CP}, \quad J_{CP} \equiv s_{12} c_{12} s_{23} c_{23} s_{13} c_{13}^2 \sin \delta_{CP}, \quad (5)$$

with positive (negative) sign for (anti-)cyclic permutation of the flavor indices e , μ and τ , and $\Delta_{ij} \equiv \Delta m_{ij}^2 L / (2E)$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$). The parameter J_{CP} is the lepton analogue of the CP -invariant factor for quarks, the unique and phase-convention-independent measure for CP violation [9].

For neutrinos traveling inside matter, coherent forward scattering induces an asymmetry between the oscillation probabilities of neutrinos and antineutrinos supplementary to the intrinsic CP violation. For the case where the matter density can be considered as constant, which is a very good approximation for an experiment like HK, one can use the same expression in Eq. (3) but just replacing the mixing matrix $U_{\alpha j}$ in vacuum to the effective one $\tilde{U}_{\alpha j}$ in constant matter density and vacuum Δm_{ij}^2 to that in matter $\Delta \tilde{m}_{ij}^2$. Exact analytic expressions for the effective mixing parameters in matter can be found in [10] whereas the approximate analytic ones can be found, e.g., in [11].

The CP violation can be studied, in principle, by comparing the oscillation probabilities for neutrino mode, $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ and antineutrino mode, $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$. In practice, such a comparison should be done based on the observables or the event number distributions for neutrino and antineutrino modes to be obtained by HK. In the upper panels of Fig. 2 we show the reconstructed neutrino energy distribution for several values of δ_{CP} expected to be observed by HK. $\sin^2 2\theta_{13} = 0.1$ and normal mass hierarchy (ordering) is assumed. In the lower panels of the same figure, we show the difference of the reconstructed neutrino energy distribution from the case with $\delta_{CP} = 0^\circ$. The error bars represent the statistical uncertainties of each bin.

FIG. 2. Top: Reconstructed neutrino energy distribution for several values of δ_{CP} . $\sin^2 2\theta_{13} = 0.1$ and normal mass hierarchy (ordering) is assumed. Bottom: Difference of the reconstructed neutrino energy distribution from the case with $\delta_{CP} = 0^\circ$. The error bars represent the statistical uncertainties of each bin. Taken from [1].

In the left panel of Fig. 3 we show the expected significance to exclude $\sin \delta_{CP} = 0$ by HK assuming the mass ordering is known to be normal, while in the right panel, we show the expected 68% CL uncertainty of δ_{CP} as a function of running time. For the normal hierarchy case, again assuming the mass ordering is known to be normal.

FIG. 3. Left panel: Expected significance to exclude $\sin \delta_{CP} = 0$ in case of normal hierarchy. Mass hierarchy is assumed to be known. Right panel: Expected 68% CL uncertainty of δ_{CP} as a function of running time. For the normal hierarchy case, and mass hierarchy is assumed to be known. Taken from [1].

B. Nucleon Decay

The sensitivities to the nucleon decay lifetime by HK depend on the decay modes. Here we describe only the 2 most sensitive decay modes for HK.

1. $p \rightarrow e^+ + \pi^0$

Proton decay into a positron and neutral pion is a favored mode in many GUT (Grand Unified Theory) models. Experimentally this decay has a very clean event topology, with no invisible particles in the final state. As a result it is possible to fully reconstruct the proton's mass from its decay products and as a two body process the total momentum of the recoiling system should be small.

In the left panel of Fig. 4 we show the comparison of the 3σ discovery potential for the $p \rightarrow e^+ + \pi^0$ decay mode as a function of year for Hyper-K (red solid) assuming a single tank as well as that of the 40 kton liquid argon detector DUNE (cyan solid) following [12]. In the orange dashed line an additional Hyper-K tank is assumed to come online six years after the start of the experiment. Super-K's discovery potential in 2026 assuming 23 years of data is also shown (by gray solid).

2. $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu} + K^+$

Proton decays into a lepton and a kaon are a feature of supersymmetric GUT, of which $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu} + K^+$ is among the most prominent. Searching for the K^+ in a water Cherenkov detector is complicated by the fact that it emerges from the decay with a momentum of only $340 \text{ MeV}/c$, well below the threshold for light production, $749 \text{ MeV}/c$. As a result the K^+ must be identified by its decay products: $K^+ \rightarrow \mu^+ + \nu$ (64% branching fraction) and $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ + \pi^0$ (21% branching fraction). Since both of these modes are two body decays the outgoing particles have monochromatic momenta. Furthermore, the 12 ns lifetime of the kaon makes it possible to observe prompt γ ray emission produced when the proton hole leftover from a bound proton decay is filled by the de-excitation of another proton. For ^{16}O nuclei the probability of producing a 6 MeV γ from such a hole is roughly 40%, making this a powerful tool for identifying the K^+ decay products and rejecting atmospheric neutrino backgrounds.

In the right panel of Fig. 4 we show comparison of the 3σ discovery potential for the $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu} + K^+$ decay mode as a function of year for the Hyper-K as well as that of the 40 kton DUNE detector

FIG. 4. Left panel: Comparison of the 3σ discovery potential for the $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ decay mode as a function of year for Hyper-K (red solid) assuming a single tank as well as that of the 40 kton liquid argon detector DUNE (cyan solid) following [12]. In the orange dashed line an additional HK tank is assumed to come online six years after the start of the experiment. Super-K’s discovery potential in 2026 assuming 23 years of data is also shown. Right panel: Comparison of the 3σ discovery potential for the $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu}K^+$ decay mode as a function of year for the Hyper-K as well as that of the 40 kton DUNE detector (cyan solid) based on [12] and the 20 kton JUNO detector based on [13]. The red line denotes a single Hyper-K tank, while the orange line shows the expectation when a second tank comes online after six years. The expected discovery potential for Super-K by 2026 assuming 23 years of data is also shown. Taken from [1].

(cyan solid) based on [12] and the 20 kton JUNO detector based on [13]. The red line denotes a single Hyper-K tank, while the orange line shows the expectation when a second tank comes online after six years. The expected discovery potential for Super-K by 2026 assuming 23 years of data is also shown.

In Fig. 5 we show the summary of the nucleon decay search, including other decay modes, indicating the current limits, theoretically expected range of nucleon lifetime, as well as the future sensitivities by DUNE and HK.

C. Neutrino Astrophysics

Hyper-K is also capable of observing neutrinos from various astrophysical objects. One of the main advantages of the detector is that its energy threshold can be set as low as several MeV, which allows us to reconstruct neutrinos from the Sun and supernovae on an event-by-event basis. Below we highlight observations of a galactic supernova by HK.

It has been difficult to successfully reproduce explosions of core-collapse supernovae (CCSN)

FIG. 5. A comparison of historical experimental limits on the rate of nucleon decay for several key modes to indicative ranges of theoretical prediction. Included in the figure are projected limits for Hyper-Kamiokande and DUNE based on 10 years of exposure. Taken from [1].

by numerical simulations for more than 40 years. However, thanks to the recent progress in modeling techniques and the growth of available computation power, multi-dimensional (2D and 3D) simulations can now lead to successful explosions, see e.g., [14, 15]. Nevertheless, there are still some puzzles, for example, the total explosion energy of the available multi-dimensional models is small compared to the SN1987A observation. Furthermore, the available 3D models are generally less energetic (or unsuccessful) compared to the more extensively simulated 2D models, see e.g., [16]. Clearly, details of the supernova explosion mechanism are still lacking, and high statistics observations of neutrinos from a CCSN by a large detector like HK and DUNE (together with gravitational waves) would be the only way to obtain precious information on the dynamics and the explosion mechanism of CCSNs.

If a CCSN explosion were to take place near the center of our Galaxy, Hyper-K would observe as many as tens of thousands of neutrino interactions. Furthermore, Hyper-K will have the ability to precisely determine the arrival time of supernova neutrinos, contributing to our understandings of both neutrino properties as well as CCSN dynamics.

In Fig. 6 we show time profiles for various interactions expected at the Hyper-K detector for a supernova at a distance of 10 kiloparsecs (kpc). This distance is a bit farther than the center of the Milky Way galaxy at 8.5 kpc; but it is chosen as being representative of what we might expect since a volume with a radius of 10 kpc centered at Earth includes about half the stars in the galaxy.

FIG. 6. Expected time profile of a supernova at 10kpc with 1 tank. Left, middle, and right panels show profiles for no oscillation, normal hierarchy, and inverted hierarchy, respectively. Black, red, purple, and light blue curves show event rates for interactions of inverse beta decay ($\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n$), νe -scattering ($\nu + e^- \rightarrow \nu + e^-$), ν_e ^{16}O CC ($\nu_e + ^{16}\text{O} \rightarrow e^- + ^{16}\text{F}^*$), and $\bar{\nu}_e$ ^{16}O CC ($\bar{\nu}_e + ^{16}\text{O} \rightarrow e^+ + ^{16}\text{N}^*$), respectively. The numbers in parentheses are integrated number of events over the burst. The fluxes and energy spectra are from the Livermore simulation [17]. Taken from [1].

FIG. 7. Left panel: Expected event rate at the time of neutronization burst for a supernova at 10kpc with 1 tank. Red and green curves show event rates for νe -scattering due to neutronization neutrino and inverse beta events, respectively. Solid, dotted, and dashed curved indicate the neutrino oscillation scenarios of no oscillation, N.H., and I.H., respectively. Right panel: Total energy spectrum for each interaction for a supernova at 10kpc with 1 tank. Black, red, purple, and light blue curves show event rates for interactions of inverse beta decay, νe -scattering, $\nu_e + ^{16}\text{O}$ CC, and $\bar{\nu}_e + ^{16}\text{O}$ CC, respectively. Solid, dashed, and dotted curves correspond to no oscillation, N.H., and I.H., respectively. Taken from [1].

In the left panel of Fig. 7 we show expected event rate at the time of neutronization burst for a supernova at 10 kpc with 1 tank. Red and green curves show event rates for νe -scattering due to neutronization neutrino and inverse beta events, respectively. Solid, dotted, and dashed curves indicate the neutrino oscillation scenarios of no oscillation, N.H., and I.H., respectively. On the other hand, in the right panel of Fig. 7 we show the total energy spectrum for each interaction for a supernova at 10 kpc with 1 tank. Black, red, purple, and light blue curves show event rates for interactions of inverse beta decay, νe -scattering, $\nu_e + {}^{16}\text{O}$ CC, and $\bar{\nu}_e + {}^{16}\text{O}$ CC, respectively. Solid, dashed, and dotted curves correspond to no oscillation, N.H., and I.H., respectively.

IV. LIST OF THE INTERESTED SCIENTISTS IN THE COMMUNITY AND POSSIBLE CONTRIBUTIONS

A. List of the interested scientists

From Latin American physics community, as far as we know, so far, only 2 faculty members from the physics department of PUC-Rio (Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brazil), Arman Esmaili and Hiroshi Nunokawa, are currently participating in the Hyper-K proto-collaboration. Considering that historically there were successful collaborations between Latin America and Japan in the area of cosmic ray physics, we consider that it would be highly welcome to have more participation in the HK project from Latin American physics community. It might also be interesting to study or discuss together with researchers participating in the DUNE project as HK is complementary to the DUNE project in the sense that the adopted neutrino detection technologies by these 2 experiments are very different, and some interesting complementarity and/or synergy can be considered.

B. Possible scientific contributions

Since we have currently only 2 members working in the area of phenomenology of neutrino physics and astrophysics from Brazil, so far our scientific contributions to the Hyper-K project has been restricted only to the theoretical ones, such as to make some contributions to the HK related documents/articles like the ones in [1, 3, 4]. Furthermore, based on the expertise we have with a lot of experience in the studies of neutrino oscillation phenomenology (see e.g., [18, 19]), currently, we are trying to explore, as much as possible, the physics potential of Hyper-K project from the theory/phenomenological point of view, mainly in the context of new physics beyond the standard model, beyond the standard three flavor mixing scheme, such as non-standard

interactions, neutrino decay, sterile neutrinos, etc. For example, we are currently finishing some phenomenological work [20] in which we study potential of HK and its second detector in Korea to probe some neutrino decay scenerios [4].

In the future, depending on the financial support we can obtain from the funding agencies, we might be able to make some contribution to the HK computing system (described in the section of computing requirements in the document) by participating in the grid computing network of HK with some lower Tier-level. Also, in the future, having participation of experimental particle physicists from Latin American community, we can extend our contribution toward hardware-oriented and/or direct contribution to the HK far detector.

V. CURRENT STATUS AND EXPECTED CHALLENGES

Currently, the Hyper-Kamiokande proto-collaboration has participation from 18 countries, 84 institutions of about 340 members. HK project has not yet been funded, therefore, the name *proto-collaboration* is currently used, but we are working to transform it to a real collaboration. Below we describe recent developments and status of the project.

On October 1, 2017, the University of Tokyo launched Next-Generation Neutrino Science Organization (NNSO)[21], where the Institute for Cosmic Ray Research, the Kavli Institute for the Physics and Mathematics of the Universe (Kavli IPMU), and the School of Science cooperate for pioneering the future of neutrino physics through the development of neutrino research techniques and detector technologies. In particular, it aims to promote what will become its flagship facility, the Hyper-Kamiokande project.

Thanks to the strong support from University of Tokyo and a good prospect for the HK project to be approved by the Japanese government, in order to discuss more details regarding the financial support for the construction of the HK detector among the participating countries, the Hyper-Kamiokande Financial Forum (HKFF) meetings were held 2 times at the University of Tokyo Campus, in January and August of 2019 (see also [21]). The 3rd HKFF meeting is expected to take place in 2020.

In August 2019, the MEXT (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology) of Japan has made some budget request for the Hyper-K project to the Ministry of Finance (MOF) of Japan for the Fiscal Year of 2020 (which starts from April 2020). The expected next step is the approval of the budget request by the MOF and the cabinet in December of 2019, and the final approval by the Diet in March 2020.

The major challenges for HK would be to: try to finalize as soon as possible all the details of

the design of the detector (as the construction will begin soon in April 2020), try to reduce the total costs for construction and operation without degrading its physics potential/sensitivities, try to increase more new participations (for the size of the project, we might need more participants).

The challenges for the local HK group in Latin America would be: trying to increase the number of participants (the 2 faculty members participating from Brazil seems to be too small to make significant contribution). Currently it is difficult to get financial support from Brazil since the economy is facing a crisis and there are huge cuts on budget for science and technology. We hope that the situation changes in the near future.

VI. TIMELINE

The construction of Hyper-K will be started in April 2020. The current plan from the finalization of the design to the completion of the production and tests are expected to proceed as follows [1].

Spring 2020: Final design review of the system

Autumn 2020: Start the design of the system based on the design review

Autumn 2021: Start bidding procedure

Autumn 2022: Start mass production

Autumn 2023: Start final system test

Autumn 2024: Complete mass production

Autumn 2025: Complete system test and get ready for install

Meanwhile, it is expected that when the HK will be officially approved/funded by the Japanese government, the HK proto-collaboration will be transformed to the HK collaboration which can happen soon. The HK detector is expected to start taking data around 2027-2028.

VII. CONSTRUCTION AND OPERATIONAL COSTS

The total costs for the construction of the first HK tank in Japan and its operational cost for 20 years were estimated, respectively, to be 67.5 and 40.0 billion Japanese yen (JPY), while the operation cost of J-PARC neutrino beam for 10 years was estimated to be 40.0 billion JPY [22]². Currently, the efforts are being made to reduce these costs.

² If we use the current (as of December 12 of 2019) exchange rate between JPY and USD, 1 USD = 109.9 JPY, 67.5 and 40.0 billion JPY correspond, respectively, to 616 and 365 million USD.

VIII. COMPUTING REQUIREMENTS

Hyper-K will adopt a Tiered computing model where Kamioka and KEK sites form the Tier-0 due to the distributed nature of the experiment. A general overview of a future Hyper-K tiered system is shown in Fig. 8.

FIG. 8. General overview of a possible Hyper-K tiered system. Taken from [1].

The Tier0 sites will hold the raw experiment data as well as the processed data. The KEK Tier0 will also contain a Tier1 center (such as RAL, TRIUMF, ccin2p3) that hold portions of the raw, processed and simulated data and provide computational resources for the simulation, processing and reprocessing. The Tier2 sites which typically consist of universities will provide computational and storage resources (the storage is usually used to hold specific subsets of the data or simulation). The model makes efficient use the available computing resources that exist at collaborating sites. The model will be regularly reviewed as changes to the computing landscape take place.

A current estimate of the rate of raw data to be stored is 20 TB/day. About 80 PB of the disk space is necessary to store the raw data for the 10 years operation. Reduction and reconstruction software will be applied to all the data in the Kamioka Tier0 as soon as the data are taken to provide different samples for different energy regions or different analysis groups, i.e. low energy region mainly for the study of solar neutrinos, higher energy for the study of nucleon decay and atmospheric neutrinos, downward going muons for the background study of solar neutrinos, the data during the beam timing from the accelerator for the beam neutrino analyses.

These data sets also provide timely feedback to the experiment and beam operation groups on

the quality of the beam and performance of the detector. Also, early detection of a supernova burst is crucial and dedicated realtime analysis has to be performed in the independent system. The required computing power for data reduction and reconstruction at this level, together with the supernova detection system, is not so huge and 1000 cores of the current Intel IA64 CPUs will be sufficient. See [1] for more details.

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